
APPLICATION OF PASSIVE COOLING TECHNIQUES IN AN INSTITUTIONAL BUILDING; A CASE STUDY OF MASS COMMUNICATION DEPARTMENT, ABDU-GUSAU POLYTECHNIC TALATA MAFARA

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed at identifying passive cooling techniques through extensive literature study that can be incorporated in an institutional building to make it energy efficient. The study also aimed at identifying changes in the design process that can affect energy efficiency in the mass communication design. It has analyzed the design features of typical mass communication buildings through a case study conducted in Abdu-Gusau polytechnic in Talata Mafara Zamfara state. However, in this research an attempt shall be made to evolve design solution with proper consideration of the climate of the site. The climatic variables directly affecting energy usage and user's comfort such as; temperature, humidity, solar radiation and air movement, are to be studied because these are the five constituents of climate that are more important for the purposes of building design. Within the context of tropical climate, with regards to this proposal, the climatic data of the study area are collected and analyzed through case study. The aim of this research is to examine the application of passive cooling techniques in an institutional building that connects the approaches of climate responsiveness in providing thermal comfort. The analyzed data shall guide us on the selection of building materials, construction method, shape and orientation of building, size and location of fenestrations and the use of soft landscape elements. These are taken into cognizance by relevant case studies and literature review of building in various climatic regions across the globe with respect to adaptability and response to various environmental variables.

Keywords: Passive Cooling Techniques, Institutional Buildings, Energy Efficiency, Thermal Comfort

INTRODUCTION

1.1 BACKGROUND OF STUDY

Passive cooling is a term used to encompass a wide range of strategies and options resulting in energy-efficient building design and increased occupant comfort. The concept emphasizes architectural design approaches that minimize building energy consumption by integrating conventional energy-efficient methods, such as building siting, an efficient envelope, appropriate amounts of fenestration, increased day lighting design, and thermal mass (Stamas & Sanford, 2008). One of the fundamental requirements of buildings is the protection of people who live and work within from the inclement of weather. The objective of environmental building design is the creation of a comfortable and energy efficient internal environment. The successful design of buildings relies on an appropriate understanding of the climatic nature of the environment. Buildings in developing countries are often designed without taking sufficient account of the climate. Factors such as the urban surroundings or site characteristics, orientation and architectural design of the building, choice of building materials, etc. are not given enough importance. Consequently buildings often have a poor indoor climate, which affects comfort, health and efficiency. The problem is found according to Rosenlund, 2000 in dwellings as well as places work and public buildings. Heating and cooling of buildings account today for high energy consumption. Higher living standards lead to active methods of adjusting the indoor climate of buildings such as offices, hotels, schools and other public buildings as well as residences. Air- conditioning plants are installed without any adaptation of the buildings to these new appliances, which leads to excessive energy consumption and high cost, and may also damage the building (Adamson & Aberg, 1993).

1.2 STATEMENT OF THE RESEARCH PROBLEM

Most buildings in developing countries are often designed without taking sufficient account of the climate. Consequently buildings often have a poor indoor climate, which affects comfort, health and efficiency. The problem is found in dwellings as well as workplaces and public buildings. Talata Mafara climate in Zamfara State is characterized as a hot-dry region. The climate is described excessive solar radiation; high daily temperature for a greater part of the year, by which to achieve energy savings and thermal comfort in buildings to be located in such region should be aimed at.

The above reasons make it essential to come up with a design of Mass Communication building for Abdu-Gusau polytechnic that will embark upon the action that is the most energy consumable 'cooling and ventilation' to reduce the carbon emission and cost of operation.

1.3 AIM

The aim of this research is to examine the application of passive cooling techniques in an institutional building that connects the approaches of climate responsiveness in providing thermal comfort.

1.4 OBJECTIVES

- i. To identify the passive cooling variables that are used in an institutional building.
- ii. To examine conventional energy consumption techniques for cooling institutional building.
- iii. To incorporate energy saving techniques and materials in the design.

1.5 RESEARCH QUESTIONS

In the cause of this research the following questions are raised to assist in research process:

- A. What are the other means available for naturally cooling of mass communication?
- B. How can these other means be applied in design?

2.1 PASSIVE DESIGN

Passive design is a term used to encompass a wide range of strategies and options resulting in energy-efficient building design and increased occupant comfort. The concept emphasizes architectural design approaches that minimize building energy consumption by integrating conventional energy-efficient methods, such as building siting, an efficient envelope, appropriate amounts of fenestration, increased day-lighting design, and thermal mass (Stamas and Sanford, 2008). Passive design involves collection, storage, distribution and control of energy flow by natural processes of cooling and ventilation. Passive becomes very effective with the use natural energy to conserve conventional energy for achieving thermal comfort. The primary objective of passive design strategies is to reduce or even eliminate the need for active mechanical systems while maintaining or even improving occupant comfort (Oikos 2008).

2.1.1 PASSIVE DESIGN STRATEGIES

Certain passive building elements have inherent synergies and can be combined to produce different and potentially greater improvements in comfort and building energy performance. However, combining elements incorrectly or using certain elements in isolation can negatively impact thermal comfort and building energy efficiency. For example, large south and west facing windows beneficial for passive solar heating must be implemented in combination with high performance windows and external shading to protect the interior from excessive solar heat gains during summer in order to achieve the desired overall building efficiency gains. It is important to note that these guidelines distinguish between cooling and ventilation (Fergus, 2008).

2.2 PASSIVE COOLING

Passive cooling is considered an "alternative" to mechanical cooling that requires complicated refrigeration systems. By employing passive cooling techniques into administrative building, mechanical cooling and will be eliminated or reduced it to a minimum. Passive cooling is based on the interaction of the building and its surroundings. Before adopting a passive cooling strategy, matching of local climate must be ensured. It is evident that the total energy consumption of buildings for cooling purposes varies as a function of the quality of design and climatic conditions (Oikos, 2008). Passive cooling strategies prevent the building from overheating by blocking solar gains and removing internal heat gains (e.g. using cooler outdoor air for ventilation, storing excess heat in thermal mass). Passive cooling strategies are often coupled with passive ventilation strategies, and the cooling function is achieved by increased passive ventilation air flow rates during periods when the outdoor air temperature is low enough to flush heat from the building (Fergus, 2008). Passive cooling is the passive design method that is required in hot dry climates as prevalent in Katsina which makes them the system to be considered for the purpose of this thesis. Heat enters and leaves a home through the roof, walls, windows and floor. Internal walls, doors and room arrangements affect heat distribution within a home. Fixed or adjustable shading devices, or shading provided by vegetation and special glazing may be used to reduce the amount of solar radiation reaching the building. External heat

gains due to solar radiation can be minimized by insulation, reduced window sizes, thermal inertia in the building envelope, reflective materials and compact building layout. Infiltration gains can be reduced by cooling the incoming air and by reducing its infiltration to a minimum necessary for comfort and health.

Figure.2.2 Passive cooling strategy, (Source Passive design toolkit, 2005)

2.2.1 PASSIVE COOLING TECHNIQUES

The passive cooling techniques which will aid the cooling of the buildings are as follows:

a) EVAPORATIVE COOLING

Evaporative cooling is a technique based on the effect of evaporation as a heat sink. Evaporative cooling lowers the indoor air temperature by evaporating water. The cooling of air is obtained as an amount of sensible heat is absorbed by the water and used as a latent source for evaporation. Evaporative cooling can be direct or indirect. In the direct method which is commonly done directly in the space, the water content of the cooled air increases, being the air in contact with the evaporated water. In the indirect methods, such as roof ponds, which allow evaporative cooling to be used in more temperate climates, the evaporation takes place inside a heat exchanger, without a change in the water content of the air. Modern systems combine the evaporation effects with the movement of the cooled air. This can happen naturally (passive evaporative cooling) or with mechanical integration (hybrid evaporative cooling). Large amounts of heat are consumed by water as it evaporates. This is called the latent heat of evaporation. This heat is partially drawn from surrounding air, causing cooling. Evaporation is an effective passive cooling method. It works best when relative humidity is lower (70 percent or less during hottest periods) and the air has a greater capacity to take up water vapor. Passive evaporative cooling design solutions include the use of pools, ponds and water features immediately outside windows or in courtyards to pre-cool air entering the house. Carefully located water features can create convective breezes (Chris, 2002).

b) HIGH THERMAL MASS

Thermal mass generally means materials capable of absorbing, holding, and gradually releasing heat (thermal energy). Thermal mass is the ability of a material to absorb heat energy. A lot of heat energy is required to change the temperature of high density materials like concrete, bricks and tiles. They are therefore said to have high thermal mass. Lightweight materials such as timber have low thermal mass. Appropriate use of thermal mass throughout a building can make a big difference to comfort and cooling bills (Chris, 2008). High thermal mass depends on the ability of materials in the building to absorb heat during the day. Each night the mass releases heat, making it ready to absorb heat again the

next day. To be effective, thermal mass must be exposed to the usable spaces. A slab floor would be an easy way to accomplish this in a design.

c) THERMAL INSULATION

Thermally insulating materials are poor thermal conductors that slow the rate of heat losses and gains to and from the outside. Effective thermal insulation is one of the most critical design parameters of building envelope. This reduction of heat transfer is expressed in terms of R- Value and U-Value. Minimum R-Values and maximum U-values for key building envelope components are prescribed by current ASHRAE 90.1 building energy standards. Any building material has an insulating effect. This is most apparent with floor coverings on concrete slabs. Timber or carpet will effectively insulate the slab and reduce (or eliminate) its effectiveness as a heat sink. Internal strapping and lining to walls will have the same effect, as will acoustic ceiling tiles.

2.2.2 TYPES OF PASSIVE COOLING SYSTEMS

A. COOLING WITH VENTILATION

- i. Comfort Ventilation: Ventilation during the day and night to increase evaporation from the skin and thereby increasing thermal comfort.
- ii. Night Flush Cooling: Ventilation to precool the building for the next day

B. RADIANT COOLING

- i. Direct Radiant Cooling: A building's roof structure cools by radiation to the night sky
- ii. Indirect Radiant Cooling: Radiation to the night sky cools a heat-transfer fluid, which then cools the building.

C. EVAPORATIVE COOLING

- i. Direct Evaporation: Water is sprayed into the air entering a building. This lowers the air's temperature but raises its humidity
- ii. Indirect Evaporative Cooling: Evaporation cools the incoming air or the building without raising the indoor humidity

D. EARTH COOLING

- i. Direct Coupling: An earth-sheltered building loses heat directly to the earth
- ii. Indirect Coupling: Air enters the building by way of earth tubes

E. DEHUMIDIFICATION WITH A DESICCANT:

- i. Removal of Latent Heat

2.2.3 PASSIVE COOLING CONTRIBUTING ELEMENTS

Elements that contribute to achievement of passive cooling include the following:

- A. Passive ventilation.
- B. Passive evaporative cooling.

- C. Thermal mass.
- D. High thermal mass with night ventilation.
- E. Central atriums and lobbies
- F. Wind towers
- G. Buffer spaces and double facades
- H. Fixed/operable external shading
- I. Low window to wall area ratio (S/W).
- J. Nocturnal cooling.
- K. Earth-tempering ducts. L. Orientation.
- M. Effective shading (including planting)
- N. Green roof.
- O. Green wall.
- P. Landscape.
- Q. Ventilated exterior wall
- R. Courtyard system.

2.2.4 PRINCIPLES OF PASSIVE COOLING TECHNIQUES

Passive cooling techniques in buildings have proven to be extremely effective and can greatly contribute in decreasing the cooling load of buildings. Efficient passive systems and techniques have been designed and tested. Passive cooling has also proven to provide excellent thermal comfort and indoor air quality, together with very low energy consumption (Matheos, 2005).

2.2.6 ARCHITECTURAL APPLICATION OF PASSIVE COOLING PRINCIPLES

The principles of passive cooling can be applied architecturally through following:

A. BUFFER SPACES

Buffer spaces such as double facades and sunspaces are located along the building perimeter and can be occupied or unoccupied, as well as semi-conditioned or unconditioned. They improve building energy performance by widening the range of outdoor temperatures in which thermal comfort can be maintained in the building with low mechanical energy consumption. Especially helpful during winter, buffer spaces create another insulation layer in front of the envelope, slowing the rate of heat loss between the outdoors and the indoor conditioned space. Ideally, they should be convertible to fully exterior space during summer

to aid in ventilation and cooling of the adjoining occupied space.

Figure 2.2.6: Double facade as buffer space (summer performance)

(Source: Passive design toolkit, (2008))

B. SITE AND ORIENTATION

Many site considerations can affect the passive design approach, including urban design opportunities and constraints, building orientation on the site, shade from other buildings, wind patterns, proximity to industry, noise, and urban character. These all need to be considered to optimize the integration of passive cooling strategies. Building facade orientation is one of the key elements for many passive design strategies. Facade orientation affects the energy and comfort implications of solar shading, window to wall area ratio, window position and performance, and choice of exterior color. A building's orientation determines the amount of solar radiation it receives. The roof surface receives the greatest intensity, but it is normally opaque and well-insulated. Building facades, which can have a significant window to wall area ratio, also receive sun in various amounts.

C. LANDSCAPE CONSIDERATIONS

Many landscape considerations happen very early on in the design process. Setbacks, street trees, street alignment and use of landscape buffer zones can be guiding elements of many site planning decisions. Therefore, careful consideration of landscaping is critical to successfully implementing the passive approach at the early stages of design.

D. SHADING DEVICES

In order to control sun penetration to the interior of buildings, it is important to provide exterior shading as part of the architectural envelope design. Such shading devices can be attached to the building or can be achieved by the articulation and disposition of the building floors to create overhangs. Exterior shading is greatly preferred over interior shading as it is important to keep the solar radiation/heat from entering the building.

2.2.7 NATURAL VENTILATION.

Natural ventilation is an important and simple technique that when appropriately used may improve thermal comfort conditions in indoor spaces, decrease the energy consumption of air conditioned buildings, and contribute to fight problems of indoor air quality by decreasing the concentration of indoor pollutants. It must be recognized that natural ventilation is not just an alternative to air conditioning. Instead it is a more effective instrument to improve indoor air quality, protect health, provide comfort, and decrease unnecessary energy consumption.

A. PRINCIPLES OF NATURAL VENTILATION

The principles of natural ventilation in buildings are relatively few and straightforward, relying on wind, thermal buoyancy or both as driving forces. There is, however, a whole range of subtle and sophisticated ways to take advantage of the natural driving forces to promote the ventilation principles. This is exemplified in a number of both new and old buildings that utilise natural driving forces for ventilation (Klieven, 2003).

B. NATURAL VENTILATION CONCEPT

The driving force is the first aspect to be applied which can be wind, buoyancy or a combination of both. While the second aspect is ventilation principle used to exploit the natural driving forces to ventilate a space. This can be done by single-sided ventilation, cross ventilation, or stack ventilation. The third aspect is the characteristic ventilation element used to realise natural ventilation. The most important characteristic elements are wind towers, wind scoops, chimneys, double façades, atria, and embedded ducts. (Source: Klieven, 2003)

C. TYPES OF NATURAL VENTILATION OPENINGS

There are several types of ventilation opening but the common ones are:

i. Single Sided Ventilation

Single sided ventilation relies on opening(s) on only one side of the ventilated enclosure. Fresh air enters the room through the same side as used air is exhausted. A typical example is the rooms of a cellular building with operable windows on one side and closed internal doors on the other side. With a single ventilation opening in the room, the main driving force in summer is wind turbulence. In cases where ventilation openings are provided at different heights within the façade, the ventilation rate can be enhanced by the buoyancy effect. The contribution from thermal buoyancy depends on the temperature difference between the inside and the outside, the vertical distance between the openings, and the area of the openings. The greater vertical distance between the openings, and the greater temperature difference between the inside and the outside, the stronger is the effect of the buoyancy. Compared with other strategies, lower ventilation rates are generated, and the ventilation air does not penetrate so far into the space (Klieven, 2003).

Figure 2.7: Single-Sided Ventilation

(Source: Passive design toolkit, 2008)

ii. Cross Ventilation

Cross-ventilation is the case when air flows between two sides of a building envelope by means of wind-induced pressure differentials between the two sides. The ventilation air enters and leaves commonly through windows, hatches or grills integrated in the façades. The ventilation air moves from the windward side to the leeward side. A typical example is an open-plan office landscape where the space stretches across the whole depth of the building.

3.1 METHODOLOGY

The research methodology adopted in this research is qualitative in nature. An extensive literature research on passive cooling and their relevance to architecture were undertaken with a view to identifying those that relate to Mass Communication department, and how they were applied previously. Detailed designs of Mass Communication (which consisted of the site plans, floor plans, and elevations) design for an already occupied by Mass Communication department, Abdu-Gusau polytechnic Talata Mafara will be collected. The floor plan analysis of all samples was undertaken to establish the extent of use of architectural spaces, places, and elements on the site and floor plans to achieve pleasant and aesthetic design. In line with the objective of this paper, an existing building of Mass Communication will be selected to demonstrate how passive cooling (thermal comfort) in Mass communication department could be integrated to achieve the said aim and objectives.

3.2 RESEARCH AREA

In view of this research due to its nature, areas related to passive cooling techniques, like courtyard, shading devices, Windows and vents, Insulation, materials selection, etc will be considered.

3.3 RESEARCH INSTRUMENTS

The research instruments used in this study to obtain information on the topic of interest are journals and case studies. The construction of a research instrument or tool for data collection is the most important aspect of a research project because anything you say in your findings or conclusions is based upon the type of information you collect. The research instruments adopted for the purpose of this work is journal, case studies, and observation. Distinct perception would be elicited from various case studies, journals and observation. Case study would be conducted so as to observe the application of passive cooling techniques in order to collect data.

3.4 TYPE OF DATA

The types of data to be use in this research for sourcing the information are: journals, case studies and observation, which usually come in prose, pictures and description; hence this made it fall under qualitative research category.

3.5 METHOD OF DATA ANALYSIS

This is the method that will be used in analyzing the data collected through journals, case studies, and observation. Content analysis is going to be used to analyze the data obtained from journals, case studies, and observation.

3.6 CASE STUDY AND OBSERVATION

Case study research in Architecture goes beyond the documentation and description of the physical characteristics of the built environment. In architectural research a case study is the most prepared mode of assessing a particular phenomenon or group of phenomena which enables the researcher to see the situation of a particular sample of the similar phenomenon thereby assessing and analyzing it (Fellows & Liu, 2021). The case studies- selected for this thesis were sampled purposively.

Case-study refers to the collection and presentation of detailed information about a particular participant or small group, frequently including the accounts of subjects themselves. A form of qualitative descriptive research, the case study looks intensely at an individual or small participant pool, drawing conclusions only about that participant or group and only in that specific context.

4.1 PASSIVE COOLING VARIABLES

The passive cooling variables are those variables responsible for cooling the building without much energy consumption. These variables include the following:

- A. Windows and vents
- B. Courtyards
- C. Orientation
- D. Roof overhangs
- E. Shading devices
- F. Materials specification
- G. Insulation
- H. Roof garden
- I. Landscaping

4.2 CASE STUDY

4.2.1 INTRODUCTION

In an attempt to provide a functional and befitting Mass Communication Department Talata Mafara, Zamfara State, the study of existing similar, relevant and related facilities around the state becomes very essential. The case studies were carried out on Mass Communication Department, Abdu-Gusau Polytechnic Talata Mafara, Zamfara State

The following criteria were tag on in the selection of case studies;-

4.2.2 DESIGN APPRAISAL

a) EXTERIOR IMAGE AND ARCHITECTURAL EXPRESSION:

This takes account of the site context and general architectural expression in terms of scale form and concept.

b) PHYSICAL ORGANISATION AND DESIGN:

This includes the zoning of related functional spaces, 1-dimensional massing of secretariat support facilities.

c) INTERIOR IMAGE:

This includes Receptions, conference Hall and offices

d) INTERACTIVITY:

This includes the provision of social spaces like main lounge, small ketchnet, stairways, seminar Hall as a board room.

e) CLIMATE ~

4.2.3 MASS COMMUNICATION DEPARTMENT IN A G P TALATA MAFARA ZAMFARA STATE

Mass communication department building, built in early 2024 and the structure is one storey floors of integrated.

4.2.4 LOCATION

Abdu Gusau Polytechnic Talata Mafara, located at Talata Mafara Local Government Area, Zamfara state.

4.2.5 DESIGN APPRAISAL

a) EXTERIOR IMAGE AND ARCHITECTURAL EXPRESSION:

The external walls have structural shading devices. The building is square in form of central reception. Its corridors are single banked which enhances ventilation flow.

b) PHYSICAL ORGANISATION AND DESIGN:

The structure is a typical office building. It has a square plan and recesses were used to introduce shade. It is the tallest building in the (Mass communication) signifying its importance.

4.2.6 GENERAL SITE PLANNING

The whole facility is design to rotate around a central core. This makes accessibility easy and quick. The longer side of the buildings is in the east west axis to limit exposure to solar. The parking lots are arranged on two wings as you approach the building from the main entrance. This arrangement reduces excessive traffic around the buildings, the building has only one vehicular rout to the site from the main entrance of the campus, There are pedestrian walkways linking to the site from other facilities around. The design concept in this building is purely functional, the concept was derived from proper use of passive cooling techniques in the design and also from selecting appropriate footprint suitable for passive cooling approach.

4.3. RESPONSIVENESS/PASSIVE COOLING VARIABLES:

How well the building envelope and its attendant elements respond to the climatic and micro-climatic conditions in which it is located. The passive cooling variables are those variables responsible for cooling the Mass communication without much energy consumption. These variables include windows and vents, orientation, roof overhangs, shading devices, materials specification, insulation, landscaping.

5.1 CONCLUSION

This research explain the current problems and provide solutions facing energy efficient design in Mass Communication buildings, in a hot dry climate by incorporating different types of passive cooling techniques to achieve energy efficiency. It has been established in this research that adoption of some passive cooling techniques like use of courtyard, optimum orientation, materials specification, roof garden, insulation, shading devices, landscaping etc can help in reducing the total energy consumption and providing thermal comfort inside the buildings. The inferences drawn from these findings are the application of some of the mentioned passive cooling techniques in the Mass Communication building designs in hot dry climate, it is possible that the Mass Communication buildings will become more viable since it will enhance the comfortable and conducive working place while not compromising the quality of the environment. It is also important that buildings are designed with the thought of reducing energy consumption by optimized building setting, orientation and proper material selection to reduce total energy consumption and the need for air conditioning. The external color and the texture of the building and the building envelope provide more effective considerable thermal comfort to the inner volumes. The objective of this research is to explore the principles of passive cooling in the design of Mass Communication building as a means of minimizing the energy consumption.

5.2 ARCHITECTURAL CONTRIBUTION

This research has highlighted the use of roof gardens, courtyard, soft landscape, Windows and vents, Orientation, Shading devices, Materials specification, Insulation, Roof overhangs etc, contributes a lot in absorbing the radiant rays acting on the roofs, the study has found out the use of ventilated exterior wall will reduce the solar heat gain to the indoor spaces from the exterior walls. The research has also demonstrated that the application of elements of passive cooling and natural ventilation will reduce the energy consumption as well as carbon emission thereby reducing the effect of global warming.

5.3 RECOMMENDATION

Well-designed energy efficient buildings maintain the best environment for human habitation while minimizing the cost of energy. The public, along with designers and clients, now realize the tremendous impact our buildings have on the natural and built environment. However, architects have to continually work towards providing friendly environment for the occupants of these buildings, let's encourage the use of architectural solutions based on the observation of natural principles that can reliably supplant artificial or mechanical means of cooling and ventilating the buildings.

It is also recommended that, further research should be carried out to explore the sufficiency of the passive means of cooling and ventilating senate buildings.

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